

Take Home Message: “Med-CORDEX coastal session”

Erika Coppola & Rosh Ranasinghe

- Med-CORDEX community is interested in expanding to coastal hazard activity development
- Coastal community very interested in engaging with Med-CORDEX community
- Med-CORDEX baseline runs will be an added value for the coastal hazard and risk projections in the Med (now fully based on GCM projections)
- There are two ways for this interaction to proceed:
 - Med-CORDEX produce the relevant high resolution estimates of waves and storm surge (dynamically coupled if possible) needed for extreme sea level and erosion estimates and the coastal community will directly use them for modelling at high resolution the coastal risk. Coastal community can help guide this process and may also be able to run a few simulations to ensure a reasonable ensemble size.
 - The coastal community will adapt its hazard and risk modelling approach for the Med sea by using as input the Med-CORDEX baseline simulations
- Both options could definitely be a possible collaboration to be funded by EU HORIZON future calls
- The coastal risk activity could become an internal Med-CORDEX activity or stay as an external one. There is interest from the coastal community to be an internal one (*contact person Rosh*) and the proposal is to have it as “internally driven activity” with contributions from externals.